

Descriptives - Motivation facet

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	13	.7054	.18773	.05207	.5919	.8188	.41	1.00
	Tim	27	.7133	.26043	.05012	.6103	.8164	.00	1.00
	Total	40	.7108	.23680	.03744	.6350	.7865	.00	1.00
Recall	Abby	13	.7508	.23368	.06481	.6096	.8920	.30	1.00
	Tim	27	.7622	.26993	.05195	.6554	.8690	.00	1.00
	Total	40	.7585	.25575	.04044	.6767	.8403	.00	1.00
FMeasure	Abby	13	.7031	.16517	.04581	.6033	.8029	.35	1.00
	Tim	27	.7185	.23426	.04508	.6258	.8112	.00	1.00
	Total	40	.7135	.21221	.03355	.6456	.7814	.00	1.00
Duration	Abby	13	746.6923	190.00499	52.69790	631.8734	861.5112	251.00	858.00
	Tim	27	630.2593	220.22534	42.38239	543.1410	717.3775	193.00	867.00
	Total	40	668.1000	215.61847	34.09227	599.1419	737.0581	193.00	867.00
FirstActDet	Abby	13	603.6923	149.10085	41.35314	513.5916	693.7931	380.00	840.00
	Tim	27	411.5926	138.52416	26.65899	356.7943	466.3909	170.00	840.00
	Total	40	474.0250	167.14058	26.42725	420.5708	527.4792	170.00	840.00
LastActDet	Abby	13	715.0769	180.82978	50.15316	605.8026	824.3513	245.00	836.00
	Tim	27	610.1852	220.39336	42.41472	523.0005	697.3699	168.00	847.00
	Total	40	644.2750	211.94109	33.51083	576.4930	712.0570	168.00	847.00
ProcDur	Abby	13	31.6154	19.19869	5.32476	20.0137	43.2170	6.00	59.00
	Tim	27	20.0741	13.95853	2.68632	14.5523	25.5959	6.00	54.00
	Total	40	23.8250	16.53107	2.61379	18.5381	29.1119	6.00	59.00
FixRel	Abby	13	1.4985	.77216	.21416	1.0319	1.9651	.25	2.85
	Tim	27	1.8019	.61397	.11816	1.5590	2.0447	.75	2.85
	Total	40	1.7033	.67489	.10671	1.4874	1.9191	.25	2.85
FixIrrel	Abby	13	3.8631	5.41036	1.50056	.5936	7.1325	.65	15.85
	Tim	27	3.8848	4.17586	.80364	2.2329	5.5367	.71	15.85
	Total	40	3.8777	4.54225	.71819	2.4251	5.3304	.65	15.85
AvDurRelFix	Abby	13	186.6731	47.50125	13.17448	157.9684	215.3778	62.75	214.50
	Tim	27	157.5648	55.05633	10.59560	135.7853	179.3444	48.25	216.75
	Total	40	167.0250	53.90462	8.52307	149.7855	184.2645	48.25	216.75
AvDurIrrelFix	Abby	13	535.0192	142.50374	39.52343	448.9051	621.1334	163.25	618.50
	Tim	27	447.6944	165.16900	31.78679	382.3558	513.0331	119.75	625.25
	Total	40	476.0750	161.71385	25.56920	424.3564	527.7936	119.75	625.25
TotSac	Abby	13	83.8462	10.88459	3.01884	77.2687	90.4236	65.00	102.00
	Tim	27	87.7037	11.10376	2.13692	83.3112	92.0962	67.00	104.00
	Total	40	86.4500	11.04524	1.74641	82.9176	89.9824	65.00	104.00
Sac2Key	Abby	13	58.3846	7.99519	2.21747	53.5532	63.2161	45.00	76.00
	Tim	27	60.6296	9.23683	1.77763	56.9757	64.2836	45.00	82.00
	Total	40	59.9000	8.81374	1.39358	57.0812	62.7188	45.00	82.00
AvAttention	Abby	13	.5000	.20412	.05661	.3766	.6234	.20	.80
	Tim	27	.5370	.20028	.03854	.4578	.6163	.20	1.00
	Total	40	.5250	.19968	.03157	.4611	.5889	.20	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	13	.4769	.21274	.05900	.3484	.6055	.20	1.00
	Tim	27	.5481	.24553	.04725	.4510	.6453	.10	1.00
	Total	40	.5250	.23507	.03717	.4498	.6002	.10	1.00
AvFam	Abby	13	.5000	.17795	.04935	.3925	.6075	.20	.70
	Tim	27	.4852	.15116	.02909	.4254	.5450	.20	.70
	Total	40	.4900	.15819	.02501	.4394	.5406	.20	.70
AvSCL	Abby	13	682.8462	135.75766	37.65240	600.8086	764.8837	475.00	824.00
	Tim	27	663.1111	135.87334	26.14884	609.3614	716.8608	373.00	868.00
	Total	40	669.5250	134.41039	21.25215	626.5385	712.5115	373.00	868.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	13	30.8562	16.52340	4.58277	20.8712	40.8411	17.41	70.71

	Tim	27	40.1511	21.18943	4.07791	31.7689	48.5334	5.92	77.27
	Total	40	37.1303	20.06924	3.17322	30.7118	43.5487	5.92	77.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	13	21.9323	18.19870	5.04741	10.9349	32.9297	1.31	43.85
	Tim	27	25.5278	19.44627	3.74244	17.8351	33.2205	2.31	58.58
	Total	40	24.3593	18.89230	2.98714	18.3172	30.4013	1.31	58.58
NASA_MD	Abby	13	70.1852	9.35224	1.79984	66.4856	73.8848	55.00	90.00
	Tim	27	59.2308	12.22125	3.38957	51.8455	66.6160	40.00	80.00
	Total	40	66.6250	11.45714	1.81153	62.9608	70.2892	40.00	90.00
NASA_PD	Abby	13	26.1538	23.99252	6.65433	11.6553	40.6524	5.00	55.00
	Tim	27	16.1111	18.25742	3.51364	8.8887	23.3335	5.00	60.00
	Total	40	19.3750	20.54350	3.24821	12.8049	25.9451	5.00	60.00
NASA_TD	Abby	13	33.0769	20.26270	5.61986	20.8323	45.3215	10.00	75.00
	Tim	27	29.2593	23.23392	4.47137	20.0682	38.4503	5.00	85.00
	Total	40	30.5000	22.12436	3.49817	23.4243	37.5757	5.00	85.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	13	65.0000	31.55683	8.75229	45.9304	84.0696	10.00	100.00
	Tim	27	57.0370	28.93159	5.56789	45.5921	68.4820	10.00	105.00
	Total	40	59.6250	29.64291	4.68696	50.1447	69.1053	10.00	105.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	13	56.5385	16.50563	4.57784	46.5642	66.5127	30.00	85.00
	Tim	27	68.5185	11.75183	2.26164	63.8697	73.1674	50.00	95.00
	Total	40	64.6250	14.42876	2.28139	60.0105	69.2395	30.00	95.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	13	50.3846	24.87146	6.89810	35.3549	65.4143	5.00	85.00
	Tim	27	44.3333	23.20477	4.46576	39.1538	57.5128	5.00	85.00
	Total	40	49.0000	23.45754	3.70896	41.4979	56.5021	5.00	85.00
NASA_Score	Abby	13	52.8738	15.97050	4.42942	43.2230	62.5247	29.00	84.67
	Tim	27	56.1744	15.74167	3.02949	49.9472	62.4016	29.00	90.00
	Total	40	55.1017	15.68854	2.48058	50.0843	60.1192	29.00	90.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Motivation facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	.012	1	31.900	.913
Recall	Welch	.019	1	27.192	.891
FMeasure	Welch	.057	1	32.451	.812
Duration	Welch	2.964	1	27.277	.044
FirstActDet	Welch	15.244	1	22.272	.051
LastActDet	Welch	2.550	1	28.561	.121
ProcDur	Welch	3.745	1	18.337	.069
FixRel	Welch	1.539	1	19.580	.229
FixIrrel	Welch	.000	1	19.144	.990
AvDurRelFix	Welch	2.964	1	27.277	.096
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	2.964	1	27.277	.096
TotSac	Welch	1.088	1	24.231	.307
Sac2Key	Welch	.624	1	27.195	.436
AvAttention	Welch	.292	1	23.384	.594
AvMentWL	Welch	.888	1	27.171	.354
AvFam	Welch	.067	1	20.637	.799
AvSCL	Welch	.185	1	23.810	.671
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	2.296	1	29.880	.140
HRVar_NN50	Welch	.327	1	25.293	.572
NASA_MD	Welch	8.147	1	19.023	.010
NASA_PD	Welch	1.781	1	18.945	.042
NASA_TD	Welch	.283	1	27.007	.048
NASA_Performance	Welch	.589	1	22.014	.451
NASA_Effort	Welch	5.505	1	18.076	.081
NASA_Frustration	Welch	.062	1	22.354	.032
NASA_Score	Welch	.378	1	23.481	.544

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

Descriptives - Information processing facet

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	27	.7996	.15948	.03069	.7365	.8627	.41	1.00
	Tim	13	.5262	.26915	.07465	.3635	.6888	.00	.87
	Total	40	.7108	.23680	.03744	.6350	.7865	.00	1.00
Recall	Abby	27	.8019	.19249	.03705	.7257	.8780	.45	1.00
	Tim	13	.6685	.34537	.09579	.4598	.8772	.00	1.00
	Total	40	.7585	.25575	.04044	.6767	.8403	.00	1.00
FMeasure	Abby	27	.7781	.12551	.02416	.7285	.8278	.50	1.00
	Tim	13	.5793	.28863	.08005	.4049	.7537	.00	.93
	Total	40	.7135	.21221	.03355	.6456	.7814	.00	1.00
Duration	Abby	27	615.8519	230.32263	44.32561	524.7393	706.9645	193.00	867.00
	Tim	13	776.6154	131.37449	36.43673	697.2266	856.0042	513.00	858.00
	Total	40	668.1000	215.61847	34.09227	599.1419	737.0581	193.00	867.00
FirstActDet	Abby	27	420.4074	134.74114	25.93094	367.1056	473.7092	170.00	705.00
	Tim	13	585.3846	177.63142	49.26609	478.0430	692.7262	350.00	840.00
	Total	40	474.0250	167.14058	26.42725	420.5708	527.4792	170.00	840.00
LastActDet	Abby	27	596.1852	230.54668	44.36873	504.9840	687.3864	168.00	847.00
	Tim	13	744.1538	121.71336	33.75721	670.6032	817.7045	494.00	838.00
	Total	40	644.2750	211.94109	33.51083	576.4930	712.0570	168.00	847.00
ProcDur	Abby	27	32.4615	15.19658	4.21477	23.2783	41.6447	11.00	55.00
	Tim	13	19.6667	15.75046	3.03118	13.4360	25.8973	6.00	59.00
	Total	40	23.8250	16.53107	2.61379	18.5381	29.1119	6.00	59.00
FixRel	Abby	27	1.8844	.56441	.10862	1.6612	2.1077	1.14	2.85
	Tim	13	1.3269	.75019	.20807	.8736	1.7803	.25	2.85
	Total	40	1.7033	.67489	.10671	1.4874	1.9191	.25	2.85
FixIrrel	Abby	27	5.2856	4.95229	.95307	3.3265	7.2446	.71	15.85
	Tim	13	.9538	.44198	.12258	.6868	1.2209	.65	1.91
	Total	40	3.8778	4.54225	.71819	2.4251	5.3304	.65	15.85
AvDurRelFix	Abby	27	153.9630	57.58066	11.08140	131.1848	176.7411	48.25	216.75
	Tim	13	194.1538	32.84362	9.10918	174.3066	214.0010	128.25	214.50
	Total	40	167.0250	53.90462	8.52307	149.7855	184.2645	48.25	216.75
AvDurIrrelFix	Abby	27	557.4615	98.53087	27.32755	497.9199	617.0031	359.75	618.50
	Tim	13	436.8889	172.74198	33.24421	368.5544	505.2233	119.75	625.25
	Total	40	476.0750	161.71385	25.56920	424.3564	527.7936	119.75	625.25
TotSac	Abby	27	86.1111	11.44328	2.20226	81.5843	90.6379	65.00	104.00
	Tim	13	87.1538	10.58179	2.93486	80.7593	93.5484	69.00	104.00
	Total	40	86.4500	11.04524	1.74641	82.9176	89.9824	65.00	104.00
Sac2Key	Abby	27	59.5926	8.79361	1.69233	56.1140	63.0712	45.00	80.00
	Tim	13	60.5385	9.17983	2.54603	54.9911	66.0858	45.00	82.00
	Total	40	59.9000	8.81374	1.39358	57.0812	62.7188	45.00	82.00
AvAttention	Abby	27	.6074	.15915	.03063	.5445	.6704	.40	1.00
	Tim	13	.3538	.16641	.04615	.2533	.4544	.20	.60
	Total	40	.5250	.19968	.03157	.4611	.5889	.20	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	27	.5926	.23358	.04495	.5002	.6850	.10	1.00
	Tim	13	.3846	.17246	.04783	.2804	.4888	.10	.70
	Total	40	.5250	.23507	.03717	.4498	.6002	.10	1.00
AvFam	Abby	27	.4630	.15229	.02931	.4027	.5232	.20	.70
	Tim	13	.5462	.16132	.04474	.4487	.6436	.30	.70
	Total	40	.4900	.15819	.02501	.4394	.5406	.20	.70
AvSCL	Abby	27	680.0741	128.74660	24.77729	629.1436	731.0045	373.00	868.00
	Tim	13	647.6154	148.42705	41.16626	557.9218	737.3090	380.00	803.00
	Total	40	669.5250	134.41039	21.25215	626.5385	712.5115	373.00	868.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	27	39.9241	21.71701	4.17944	31.3331	48.5150	5.92	77.27

	Tim	13	31.3277	15.26817	4.23463	22.1012	40.5542	19.97	70.96
	Total	40	37.1303	20.06924	3.17322	30.7118	43.5487	5.92	77.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	27	25.3896	19.30093	3.71447	17.7544	33.0248	1.31	58.58
	Tim	13	22.2192	18.58756	5.15526	10.9869	33.4516	2.31	55.07
	Total	40	24.3593	18.89230	2.98714	18.3172	30.4013	1.31	58.58
NASA_MD	Abby	27	69.2593	12.22416	2.35254	64.4235	74.0950	40.00	90.00
	Tim	13	61.1538	7.40322	2.05328	56.6801	65.6276	55.00	80.00
	Total	40	66.6250	11.45714	1.81153	62.9608	70.2892	40.00	90.00
NASA_PD	Abby	27	33.4615	22.39649	6.21167	19.9275	46.9956	5.00	55.00
	Tim	13	12.5926	15.95489	3.07052	6.2810	18.9041	5.00	60.00
	Total	40	19.3750	20.54350	3.24821	12.8049	25.9451	5.00	60.00
NASA_TD	Abby	27	31.6667	24.33737	4.68373	22.0391	41.2942	5.00	85.00
	Tim	13	28.0769	17.26490	4.78842	17.6438	38.5100	5.00	45.00
	Total	40	30.5000	22.12436	3.49817	23.4243	37.5757	5.00	85.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	27	60.3704	28.17957	5.42316	49.2229	71.5178	10.00	105.00
	Tim	13	58.0769	33.63644	9.32907	37.7506	78.4032	10.00	90.00
	Total	40	59.6250	29.64291	4.68696	50.1447	69.1053	10.00	105.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	27	67.0370	15.33343	2.95092	60.9713	73.1027	30.00	95.00
	Tim	13	59.6154	11.26601	3.12463	52.8074	66.4234	50.00	85.00
	Total	40	64.6250	14.42876	2.28139	60.0105	69.2395	30.00	95.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	27	51.4815	21.60906	4.15867	42.9332	60.0297	5.00	85.00
	Tim	13	43.8462	27.09196	7.51396	27.4746	60.2177	5.00	75.00
	Total	40	49.0000	23.45754	3.70896	41.4979	56.5021	5.00	85.00
NASA_Score	Abby	27	57.3348	15.85408	3.05112	51.0631	63.6065	29.00	90.00
	Tim	13	50.4638	14.85952	4.12129	41.4843	59.4434	29.00	73.67
	Total	40	55.1017	15.68854	2.48058	50.0843	60.1192	29.00	90.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Information processing facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	11.480	1	16.187	.004
Recall	Welch	1.687	1	15.696	.032
FMeasure	Welch	5.656	1	14.230	.213
Duration	Welch	7.850	1	36.701	.081
FirstActDet	Welch	8.781	1	18.900	.080
LastActDet	Welch	7.044	1	37.551	.051
ProcDur	Welch	6.074	1	24.588	.021
FixRel	Welch	5.642	1	18.788	.082
FixIrrel	Welch	20.321	1	26.851	.000
AvDurRelFix	Welch	7.850	1	36.701	.008
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	7.850	1	36.701	.008
TotSac	Welch	.081	1	25.576	.779
Sac2Key	Welch	.096	1	22.884	.760
AvAttention	Welch	20.954	1	22.851	.000
AvMentWL	Welch	10.039	1	31.291	.003
AvFam	Welch	2.419	1	22.587	.134
AvSCL	Welch	.456	1	20.997	.507
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	2.088	1	32.522	.016
HRVar_NN50	Welch	.249	1	24.630	.622
NASA_MD	Welch	6.738	1	35.750	.014
NASA_PD	Welch	9.071	1	18.083	.007
NASA_TD	Welch	.287	1	32.300	.596
NASA_Performance	Welch	.045	1	20.405	.834
NASA_Effort	Welch	2.982	1	31.417	.044
NASA_Frustration	Welch	.790	1	19.628	.385
NASA_Score	Welch	1.795	1	25.257	.192

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

Descriptives - Self-efficacy facet

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	22	.7459	.21975	.04685	.6485	.8433	.00	1.00
	Tim	18	.6678	.25579	.06029	.5406	.7950	.00	1.00
	Total	40	.7107	.23680	.03744	.6350	.7865	.00	1.00
Recall	Abby	22	.7777	.25109	.05353	.6664	.8891	.00	1.00
	Tim	18	.7350	.26666	.06285	.6024	.8676	.00	1.00
	Total	40	.7585	.25575	.04044	.6767	.8403	.00	1.00
FMeasure	Abby	22	.7421	.19866	.04235	.6540	.8302	.00	1.00
	Tim	18	.6785	.22848	.05385	.5649	.7922	.00	1.00
	Total	40	.7135	.21221	.03355	.6456	.7814	.00	1.00
Duration	Abby	22	602.7727	227.32815	48.46652	501.9811	703.5644	193.00	850.00
	Tim	18	747.9444	174.77396	41.19462	661.0314	834.8575	264.00	867.00
	Total	40	668.1000	215.61847	34.09227	599.1419	737.0581	193.00	867.00
FirstActDet	Abby	22	529.8333	175.75593	41.42607	442.4320	617.2347	205.00	840.00
	Tim	18	428.3636	148.39444	31.63780	362.5692	494.1580	170.00	840.00
	Total	40	474.0250	167.14058	26.42725	420.5708	527.4792	170.00	840.00
LastActDet	Abby	22	583.0455	228.21804	48.65625	481.8592	684.2317	168.00	836.00
	Tim	18	719.1111	167.12126	39.39086	636.0037	802.2186	258.00	847.00
	Total	40	644.2750	211.94109	33.51083	576.4930	712.0570	168.00	847.00
ProcDur	Abby	22	19.7273	13.93585	2.97113	13.5485	25.9061	6.00	54.00
	Tim	18	28.8333	18.40476	4.33804	19.6809	37.9858	6.00	59.00
	Total	40	23.8250	16.53107	2.61379	18.5381	29.1119	6.00	59.00
FixRel	Abby	22	1.7518	.57579	.12276	1.4965	2.0071	.90	2.85
	Tim	18	1.6439	.79284	.18687	1.2496	2.0382	.25	2.85
	Total	40	1.7033	.67489	.10671	1.4874	1.9191	.25	2.85
FixIrrel	Abby	22	4.9114	4.93939	1.05308	2.7214	7.1014	.71	15.85
	Tim	18	2.6144	3.75789	.88574	.7457	4.4832	.65	15.85
	Total	40	3.8777	4.54225	.71819	2.4251	5.3304	.65	15.85
AvDurRelFix	Abby	22	150.6932	56.83204	12.11663	125.4953	175.8911	48.25	212.50
	Tim	18	186.9861	43.69349	10.29865	165.2578	208.7144	66.00	216.75
	Total	40	167.0250	53.90462	8.52307	149.7855	184.2645	48.25	216.75
AvDurIrrelFix	Abby	22	535.9583	131.08047	30.89596	470.7735	601.1431	173.00	625.25
	Tim	18	427.0795	170.49611	36.34989	351.4858	502.6733	119.75	612.50
	Total	40	476.0750	161.71385	25.56920	424.3564	527.7936	119.75	625.25
TotSac	Abby	22	86.4091	12.41604	2.64711	80.9041	91.9141	65.00	104.00
	Tim	18	86.5000	9.45733	2.22912	81.7970	91.2030	69.00	104.00
	Total	40	86.4500	11.04524	1.74641	82.9176	89.9824	65.00	104.00
Sac2Key	Abby	22	60.8182	10.43180	2.22407	56.1930	65.4434	45.00	82.00
	Tim	18	58.7778	6.43113	1.51583	55.5797	61.9759	45.00	71.00
	Total	40	59.9000	8.81374	1.39358	57.0812	62.7188	45.00	82.00
AvAttention	Abby	22	.5591	.19435	.04143	.4729	.6453	.20	1.00
	Tim	18	.4833	.20364	.04800	.3821	.5846	.20	.80
	Total	40	.5250	.19968	.03157	.4611	.5889	.20	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	22	.5909	.22868	.04875	.4895	.6923	.20	1.00
	Tim	18	.4444	.22287	.05253	.3336	.5553	.10	1.00
	Total	40	.5250	.23507	.03717	.4498	.6002	.10	1.00
AvFam	Abby	22	.4727	.15486	.03302	.4041	.5414	.20	.70
	Tim	18	.5111	.16410	.03868	.4295	.5927	.20	.70
	Total	40	.4900	.15819	.02501	.4394	.5406	.20	.70
AvSCL	Abby	22	681.5000	149.81187	31.94000	615.0771	747.9229	373.00	868.00
	Tim	18	654.8889	115.36484	27.19175	597.5193	712.2585	463.00	803.00
	Total	40	669.5250	134.41039	21.25215	626.5385	712.5115	373.00	868.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	22	39.7495	21.63143	4.61184	30.1587	49.3404	9.62	77.27

	Tim	18	33.9289	18.06279	4.25744	24.9465	42.9113	5.92	73.83
	Total	40	37.1303	20.06924	3.17322	30.7118	43.5487	5.92	77.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	22	25.8609	20.28780	4.32537	16.8658	34.8560	1.31	58.58
	Tim	18	22.5239	17.43241	4.10886	13.8550	31.1928	2.31	51.97
	Total	40	24.3593	18.89230	2.98714	18.3172	30.4013	1.31	58.58
NASA_MD	Abby	22	69.5455	11.74218	2.50344	64.3393	74.7516	40.00	90.00
	Tim	18	63.0556	10.30975	2.43003	57.9286	68.1825	40.00	80.00
	Total	40	66.6250	11.45714	1.81153	62.9608	70.2892	40.00	90.00
NASA_PD	Abby	22	23.3333	21.82821	5.14496	12.4784	34.1882	5.00	55.00
	Tim	18	16.1364	19.32996	4.12116	7.5659	24.7068	5.00	60.00
	Total	40	19.3750	20.54350	3.24821	12.8049	25.9451	5.00	60.00
NASA_TD	Abby	22	32.2727	24.18812	5.15692	21.5483	42.9971	5.00	85.00
	Tim	18	28.3333	19.77818	4.66176	18.4979	38.1688	5.00	75.00
	Total	40	30.5000	22.12436	3.49817	23.4243	37.5757	5.00	85.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	22	63.4091	27.74829	5.91596	51.1062	75.7120	25.00	105.00
	Tim	18	55.0000	31.99265	7.54074	39.0904	70.9096	10.00	100.00
	Total	40	59.6250	29.64291	4.68696	50.1447	69.1053	10.00	105.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	22	67.5000	15.09888	3.21909	60.8055	74.1945	30.00	95.00
	Tim	18	61.1111	13.12335	3.09320	54.5850	67.6372	30.00	85.00
	Total	40	64.6250	14.42876	2.28139	60.0105	69.2395	30.00	95.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	22	53.4091	20.55112	4.38151	44.2972	62.5209	25.00	85.00
	Tim	18	43.6111	26.16720	6.16767	30.5985	56.6238	5.00	85.00
	Total	40	49.0000	23.45754	3.70896	41.4979	56.5021	5.00	85.00
NASA_Score	Abby	22	58.3805	15.48591	3.30161	51.5144	65.2465	35.67	90.00
	Tim	18	51.0944	15.41093	3.63239	43.4308	58.7581	29.00	84.67
	Total	40	55.1018	15.68854	2.48058	50.0843	60.1192	29.00	90.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Self-efficacy facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	1.047	1	33.764	.313
Recall	Welch	.268	1	35.491	.608
FMeasure	Welch	.861	1	34.003	.360
Duration	Welch	5.209	1	37.880	.058
FirstActDet	Welch	3.789	1	33.413	.036
LastActDet	Welch	4.724	1	37.597	.060
ProcDur	Welch	2.999	1	31.142	.093
FixRel	Welch	.233	1	30.274	.633
FixIrrel	Welch	2.786	1	37.833	.010
AvDurRelFix	Welch	5.209	1	37.880	.028
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	5.209	1	37.880	.028
TotSac	Welch	.001	1	37.839	.979
Sac2Key	Welch	.575	1	35.562	.453
AvAttention	Welch	1.427	1	35.719	.040
AvMentWL	Welch	4.176	1	36.798	.048
AvFam	Welch	.570	1	35.530	.056
AvSCL	Welch	.402	1	37.887	.530
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	.860	1	37.975	.360
HRVar_NN50	Welch	.313	1	37.888	.579
NASA_MD	Welch	3.460	1	37.782	.041
NASA_PD	Welch	1.192	1	34.362	.028
NASA_TD	Welch	.321	1	37.999	.574
NASA_Performance	Welch	.770	1	33.954	.386
NASA_Effort	Welch	2.048	1	37.836	.161
NASA_Frustration	Welch	1.677	1	31.909	.205
NASA_Score	Welch	2.203	1	36.516	.146

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

Descriptives - Risk facet									
		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	15	.8060	.21213	.05477	.6885	.9235	.41	1.00
	Tim	25	.6536	.23622	.04724	.5561	.7511	.00	1.00
	Total	40	.7107	.23680	.03744	.6350	.7865	.00	1.00
Recall	Abby	15	.7540	.19584	.05057	.6455	.8625	.30	1.00
	Tim	25	.7612	.28965	.05793	.6416	.8808	.00	1.00
	Total	40	.7585	.25575	.04044	.6767	.8403	.00	1.00
FMeasure	Abby	15	.7621	.17668	.04562	.6643	.8600	.35	1.00
	Tim	25	.6843	.22936	.04587	.5897	.7790	.00	.92
	Total	40	.7135	.21221	.03355	.6456	.7814	.00	1.00
Duration	Abby	15	707.8667	242.28875	62.55869	573.6916	842.0417	193.00	858.00
	Tim	25	644.2400	199.30656	39.86131	561.9703	726.5097	251.00	867.00
	Total	40	668.1000	215.61847	34.09227	599.1419	737.0581	193.00	867.00
FirstActDet	Abby	15	548.9333	221.71232	57.24587	426.1531	671.7135	170.00	840.00
	Tim	25	429.0800	105.40474	21.08095	385.5711	472.5889	205.00	667.00
	Total	40	474.0250	167.14058	26.42725	420.5708	527.4792	170.00	840.00
LastActDet	Abby	15	665.2667	239.33344	61.79563	532.7282	797.8051	168.00	825.00
	Tim	25	631.6800	197.83615	39.56723	550.0172	713.3428	245.00	847.00
	Total	40	644.2750	211.94109	33.51083	576.4930	712.0570	168.00	847.00
ProcDur	Abby	15	42.6000	10.66905	2.75474	36.6917	48.5083	15.00	59.00
	Tim	25	12.5600	5.01730	1.00346	10.4890	14.6310	6.00	20.00
	Total	40	23.8250	16.53107	2.61379	18.5381	29.1119	6.00	59.00
FixRel	Abby	15	1.3880	.66525	.17177	1.0196	1.7564	.25	2.85
	Tim	25	1.8924	.61855	.12371	1.6371	2.1477	.75	2.85
	Total	40	1.7033	.67489	.10671	1.4874	1.9191	.25	2.85
FixIrrel	Abby	15	4.0447	5.22502	1.34909	1.1511	6.9382	.65	15.85
	Tim	25	3.7776	4.19210	.83842	2.0472	5.5080	.71	15.85
	Total	40	3.8777	4.54225	.71819	2.4251	5.3304	.65	15.85
AvDurRelFix	Abby	15	176.9667	60.57219	15.63967	143.4229	210.5104	48.25	214.50
	Tim	25	161.0600	49.82664	9.96533	140.4926	181.6274	62.75	216.75
	Total	40	167.0250	53.90462	8.52307	149.7855	184.2645	48.25	216.75
AvDurlrrelFix	Abby	15	505.9000	181.71656	46.91901	405.2687	606.5313	119.75	618.50
	Tim	25	458.1800	149.47992	29.89598	396.4777	519.8823	163.25	625.25
	Total	40	476.0750	161.71385	25.56920	424.3564	527.7936	119.75	625.25
TotSac	Abby	15	86.1333	8.76573	2.26330	81.2790	90.9876	67.00	97.00
	Tim	25	86.6400	12.38238	2.47648	81.5288	91.7512	65.00	104.00
	Total	40	86.4500	11.04524	1.74641	82.9176	89.9824	65.00	104.00
Sac2Key	Abby	15	59.0667	7.91442	2.04350	54.6838	63.4495	45.00	80.00
	Tim	25	60.4000	9.43398	1.88680	56.5058	64.2942	45.00	82.00
	Total	40	59.9000	8.81374	1.39358	57.0812	62.7188	45.00	82.00
AvAttention	Abby	15	.4667	.18387	.04748	.3648	.5685	.20	.70
	Tim	25	.5600	.20412	.04082	.4757	.6443	.20	1.00
	Total	40	.5250	.19968	.03157	.4611	.5889	.20	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	15	.4333	.21269	.05492	.3155	.5511	.20	1.00
	Tim	25	.5800	.23452	.04690	.4832	.6768	.10	1.00
	Total	40	.5250	.23507	.03717	.4498	.6002	.10	1.00
AvFam	Abby	15	.5267	.16242	.04194	.4367	.6166	.30	.70
	Tim	25	.4680	.15470	.03094	.4041	.5319	.20	.70
	Total	40	.4900	.15819	.02501	.4394	.5406	.20	.70
AvSCL	Abby	15	666.8000	141.07759	36.42608	588.6738	744.9262	475.00	868.00
	Tim	25	671.1600	133.19180	26.63836	616.1811	726.1389	373.00	833.00
	Total	40	669.5250	134.41039	21.25215	626.5385	712.5115	373.00	868.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	15	23.9287	7.55111	1.94969	19.7470	28.1103	9.62	35.64

	Tim	25	45.0512	21.14155	4.22831	36.3244	53.7780	5.92	77.27
	Total	40	37.1303	20.06924	3.17322	30.7118	43.5487	5.92	77.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	15	16.5820	15.48031	3.99700	8.0093	25.1547	2.31	41.14
	Tim	25	29.0256	19.48635	3.89727	20.9820	37.0692	1.31	58.58
	Total	40	24.3593	18.89230	2.98714	18.3172	30.4013	1.31	58.58
NASA_MD	Abby	15	65.3333	14.07463	3.63405	57.5391	73.1276	40.00	90.00
	Tim	25	67.4000	9.80221	1.96044	63.3538	71.4462	40.00	80.00
	Total	40	66.6250	11.45714	1.81153	62.9608	70.2892	40.00	90.00
NASA_PD	Abby	15	30.3333	24.81839	6.40808	16.5894	44.0773	5.00	60.00
	Tim	25	12.8000	14.36721	2.87344	6.8695	18.7305	5.00	55.00
	Total	40	19.3750	20.54350	3.24821	12.8049	25.9451	5.00	60.00
NASA_TD	Abby	15	42.6667	26.31313	6.79402	28.0949	57.2384	10.00	85.00
	Tim	25	23.2000	15.60449	3.12090	16.7588	29.6412	5.00	50.00
	Total	40	30.5000	22.12436	3.49817	23.4243	37.5757	5.00	85.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	15	73.3333	30.97618	7.99802	56.1793	90.4874	10.00	105.00
	Tim	25	51.4000	26.08160	5.21632	40.6340	62.1660	10.00	90.00
	Total	40	59.6250	29.64291	4.68696	50.1447	69.1053	10.00	105.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	15	60.0000	15.81139	4.08248	51.2439	68.7561	30.00	95.00
	Tim	25	67.4000	13.07988	2.61598	62.0009	72.7991	30.00	85.00
	Total	40	64.6250	14.42876	2.28139	60.0105	69.2395	30.00	95.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	15	58.3333	26.02654	6.72002	43.9203	72.7464	5.00	85.00
	Tim	25	43.4000	20.29573	4.05915	35.0223	51.7777	5.00	75.00
	Total	40	49.0000	23.45754	3.70896	41.4979	56.5021	5.00	85.00
NASA_Score	Abby	15	60.7133	18.82520	4.86065	50.2883	71.1384	29.00	90.00
	Tim	25	51.7348	12.71792	2.54358	46.4851	56.9845	29.00	73.67
	Total	40	55.1017	15.68854	2.48058	50.0843	60.1192	29.00	90.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Risk facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	4.439	1	32.189	.043
Recall	Welch	.009	1	37.342	.926
FMeasure	Welch	1.445	1	35.471	.237
Duration	Welch	.736	1	25.248	.399
FirstActDet	Welch	3.860	1	17.863	.045
LastActDet	Welch	.210	1	25.347	.651
ProcDur	Welch	104.985	1	17.779	.054
FixRel	Welch	5.678	1	27.910	.052
FixIrrel	Welch	.028	1	24.749	.868
AvDurRelFix	Welch	.736	1	25.248	.399
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	.736	1	25.248	.399
TotSac	Welch	.023	1	36.811	.881
Sac2Key	Welch	.230	1	33.741	.635
AvAttention	Welch	2.222	1	32.116	.146
AvMentWL	Welch	4.124	1	31.956	.051
AvFam	Welch	1.267	1	28.469	.270
AvSCL	Welch	.009	1	28.263	.924
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	20.580	1	32.752	.000
HRVar_NN50	Welch	4.969	1	34.882	.052
NASA_MD	Welch	.251	1	22.236	.622
NASA_PD	Welch	6.233	1	19.731	.022
NASA_TD	Welch	6.779	1	20.012	.017
NASA_Performance	Welch	5.276	1	25.728	.060
NASA_Effort	Welch	2.329	1	25.363	.139
NASA_Frustration	Welch	3.618	1	24.201	.039
NASA_Score	Welch	2.679	1	21.765	.116

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

Descriptives - Learning style facet

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	10	.5400	.23152	.07321	.3744	.7056	.00	.87
	Tim	30	.7677	.21300	.03889	.6881	.8472	.00	1.00
	Total	40	.7108	.23680	.03744	.6350	.7865	.00	1.00
Recall	Abby	10	.7060	.31592	.09990	.4800	.9320	.00	1.00
	Tim	30	.7760	.23605	.04310	.6879	.8641	.00	1.00
	Total	40	.7585	.25575	.04044	.6767	.8403	.00	1.00
FMeasure	Abby	10	.6042	.25811	.08162	.4196	.7889	.00	.93
	Tim	30	.7499	.18546	.03386	.6807	.8192	.00	1.00
	Total	40	.7135	.21221	.03355	.6456	.7814	.00	1.00
Duration	Abby	10	736.1000	167.65537	53.01728	616.1666	856.0334	470.00	858.00
	Tim	30	645.4333	227.31820	41.50244	560.5513	730.3153	193.00	867.00
	Total	40	668.1000	215.61847	34.09227	599.1419	737.0581	193.00	867.00
FirstActDet	Abby	10	585.4000	161.67058	51.12473	469.7478	701.0522	399.00	840.00
	Tim	30	436.9000	154.12430	28.13912	379.3490	494.4510	170.00	840.00
	Total	40	474.0250	167.14058	26.42725	420.5708	527.4792	170.00	840.00
LastActDet	Abby	10	705.2000	153.42519	48.51731	595.4462	814.9538	464.00	825.00
	Tim	30	623.9667	226.70785	41.39100	539.3126	708.6208	168.00	847.00
	Total	40	644.2750	211.94109	33.51083	576.4930	712.0570	168.00	847.00
ProcDur	Abby	10	30.9000	17.34903	5.48625	18.4893	43.3107	6.00	59.00
	Tim	30	21.4667	15.84566	2.89301	15.5498	27.3835	6.00	55.00
	Total	40	23.8250	16.53107	2.61379	18.5381	29.1119	6.00	59.00
FixRel	Abby	10	1.4270	.82207	.25996	.8389	2.0151	.25	2.85
	Tim	30	1.7953	.60640	.11071	1.5689	2.0218	.75	2.85
	Total	40	1.7033	.67489	.10671	1.4874	1.9191	.25	2.85
Fixlrrrel	Abby	10	4.8703	4.86050	.88740	3.0554	6.6853	.71	15.85
	Tim	30	.9000	.38195	.12078	.6268	1.1732	.65	1.91
	Total	40	3.8778	4.54225	.71819	2.4251	5.3304	.65	15.85
AvDurRelFix	Abby	10	161.3583	56.82955	10.37561	140.1378	182.5788	48.25	216.75
	Tim	30	184.0250	41.91384	13.25432	154.0416	214.0084	117.50	214.50
	Total	40	167.0250	53.90462	8.52307	149.7855	184.2645	48.25	216.75
AvDurlrrrelFix	Abby	10	527.0750	125.74153	39.76296	437.1249	617.0251	327.50	618.50
	Tim	30	459.0750	170.48865	31.12683	395.4135	522.7365	119.75	625.25
	Total	40	476.0750	161.71385	25.56920	424.3564	527.7936	119.75	625.25
TotSac	Abby	10	88.1000	10.72329	3.39100	80.4290	95.7710	73.00	104.00
	Tim	30	85.9000	11.27509	2.05854	81.6898	90.1102	65.00	104.00
	Total	40	86.4500	11.04524	1.74641	82.9176	89.9824	65.00	104.00
Sac2Key	Abby	10	62.0000	8.02773	2.53859	56.2573	67.7427	55.00	82.00
	Tim	30	59.2000	9.07972	1.65772	55.8096	62.5904	45.00	80.00
	Total	40	59.9000	8.81374	1.39358	57.0812	62.7188	45.00	82.00
AvAttention	Abby	10	.3700	.15670	.04955	.2579	.4821	.20	.60
	Tim	30	.5767	.18696	.03413	.5069	.6465	.20	1.00
	Total	40	.5250	.19968	.03157	.4611	.5889	.20	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	10	.4400	.17764	.05617	.3129	.5671	.20	.70
	Tim	30	.5533	.24738	.04516	.4610	.6457	.10	1.00
	Total	40	.5250	.23507	.03717	.4498	.6002	.10	1.00
AvFam	Abby	10	.5500	.17795	.05627	.4227	.6773	.30	.70
	Tim	30	.4700	.14890	.02719	.4144	.5256	.20	.70
	Total	40	.4900	.15819	.02501	.4394	.5406	.20	.70
AvSCL	Abby	10	631.4000	161.94251	51.21072	515.5533	747.2467	380.00	803.00
	Tim	30	682.2333	124.45348	22.72199	635.7616	728.7050	373.00	868.00
	Total	40	669.5250	134.41039	21.25215	626.5385	712.5115	373.00	868.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	10	29.9740	15.97133	5.05058	18.5488	41.3992	19.97	70.96

	Tim	30	39.5157	20.95119	3.82515	31.6924	47.3390	5.92	77.27
	Total	40	37.1303	20.06924	3.17322	30.7118	43.5487	5.92	77.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	10	22.6810	19.65716	6.21614	8.6191	36.7429	2.31	55.07
	Tim	30	24.9187	18.94152	3.45823	17.8458	31.9915	1.31	58.58
	Total	40	24.3593	18.89230	2.98714	18.3172	30.4013	1.31	58.58
NASA_MD	Abby	10	62.5000	7.90569	2.50000	56.8446	68.1554	55.00	80.00
	Tim	30	68.0000	12.21926	2.23092	63.4373	72.5627	40.00	90.00
	Total	40	66.6250	11.45714	1.81153	62.9608	70.2892	40.00	90.00
NASA_PD	Abby	10	31.0000	22.82786	7.21880	14.6699	47.3301	5.00	55.00
	Tim	30	15.5000	18.53933	3.38480	8.5773	22.4227	5.00	60.00
	Total	40	19.3750	20.54350	3.24821	12.8049	25.9451	5.00	60.00
NASA_TD	Abby	10	29.0000	18.67857	5.90668	15.6382	42.3618	5.00	50.00
	Tim	30	31.0000	23.43001	4.27772	22.2511	39.7489	5.00	85.00
	Total	40	30.5000	22.12436	3.49817	23.4243	37.5757	5.00	85.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	10	55.5000	34.43593	10.88960	30.8660	80.1340	10.00	90.00
	Tim	30	61.0000	28.38771	5.18286	50.3999	71.6001	10.00	105.00
	Total	40	59.6250	29.64291	4.68696	50.1447	69.1053	10.00	105.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	10	60.5000	11.41393	3.60940	52.3350	68.6650	50.00	85.00
	Tim	30	66.0000	15.22249	2.77923	60.3158	71.6842	30.00	95.00
	Total	40	64.6250	14.42876	2.28139	60.0105	69.2395	30.00	95.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	10	45.0000	26.56230	8.39974	25.9985	64.0015	5.00	75.00
	Tim	30	50.3333	22.66447	4.13795	41.8703	58.7964	5.00	85.00
	Total	40	49.0000	23.45754	3.70896	41.4979	56.5021	5.00	85.00
NASA_Score	Abby	10	50.2360	15.10075	4.77528	39.4336	61.0384	29.00	73.67
	Tim	30	56.7237	15.79078	2.88299	50.8273	62.6200	29.00	90.00
	Total	40	55.1018	15.68854	2.48058	50.0843	60.1192	29.00	90.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Learning style facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	7.542	1	14.439	.192
Recall	Welch	.414	1	12.527	.532
FMeasure	Welch	2.718	1	12.252	.125
Duration	Welch	1.813	1	20.966	.019
FirstActDet	Welch	6.475	1	14.856	.023
LastActDet	Welch	1.622	1	23.075	.215
ProcDur	Welch	2.313	1	14.357	.150
FixRel	Welch	1.699	1	12.434	.216
FixIrrel	Welch	19.654	1	30.051	.000
AvDurRelFix	Welch	1.813	1	20.966	.039
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	1.813	1	20.966	.048
TotSac	Welch	.308	1	16.174	.587
Sac2Key	Welch	.853	1	17.334	.037
AvAttention	Welch	11.796	1	18.289	.053
AvMentWL	Welch	2.472	1	21.596	.130
AvFam	Welch	1.639	1	13.464	.222
AvSCL	Welch	.823	1	12.739	.381
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	2.268	1	20.221	.148
HRVar_NN50	Welch	.099	1	14.988	.757
NASA_MD	Welch	2.694	1	24.266	.114
NASA_PD	Welch	3.779	1	13.194	.044
NASA_TD	Welch	.075	1	19.271	.787
NASA_Performance	Welch	.208	1	13.327	.656
NASA_Effort	Welch	1.458	1	20.590	.241
NASA_Frustration	Welch	.324	1	13.649	.578
NASA_Score	Welch	1.353	1	16.093	.262

a. Asymptotically F distributed.